

United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization

31st August 2024

Working Paper Boom Shaka Laka Boom Boom

Agenda: *Addressing the lingering impact of neo-colonialism in Educational and social spheres*

Sponsors: *Islamic Republic of Pakistan, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland*

Signatories: United States of America, Republic of Kenya, Republic of Mozambique, Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela, Republic of Ghana, Republic of Colombia, Commonwealth of Australia, Republic of the Union of Myanmar, Republic of South Africa, Republic of Portugal, Islamic Republic of Pakistan, Burkina Faso, People's Republic of Bangladesh, Republic of Uganda, Federal Republic of Nigeria, Russian Federation, Republic of Zimbabwe, Republic of France, People's Republic of China, United Mexican States, Republic of Madagascar, Republic of Cuba, Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, Independent State of Papua New Guinea

Operative Clauses

Urges member states to ensure the protection of Indigenous cultures and educational systems by:

- a) Developing policies that protect and promote indigenous knowledge and languages,
- b) Integrating indigenous languages, histories, and traditional ecological knowledge into school curricula,
- c) Reforming cultural Education models to include diverse cultural perspectives and knowledge systems,

- d) Ensuring that curricula reflect the values and experiences of various indigenous communities ;

Further encourages member states to mitigate the effect of brain drain by:

- a) Implementing policies to improve job satisfaction,
- b) Improving working conditions,
- c) Taking steps to contribute to the creation of more jobs by investing in areas that are not developing,
- d) Investing in state of the art research facilities and encouraging collaboration between institutions, researchers, and professionals,
- e) Establishing strong startup culture , with special focus on businesses led by returnees and expatriates, providing them with resources and incentives;

Encourages diversifying economies of member states and reducing dependency on other states along with:-

- a)Support for domestic industries through local production leading to innovation and competition in the global market,
- b)Support for environmentally sustainable trade practices,
- c)Support for Small & Medium-Sized Enterprises and Entrepreneurship for local growth and fostering of the state;

Recommends to strengthen the articles stated in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People and ensure that the strengthened articles are upheld in practice;

Suggests to fund and collaborate on an international agency under the UNESCO comprised of officials making documents aimed at preserving indigenous languages, cultures and rights, as mentioned in Annexure I;

Suggests to develop and expand educational exchange programs that focus on indigenous knowledge and perspectives that can:

- (i) help integrate indigenous ways of knowing into mainstream education,
- (ii) promote mutual respect and understanding;

Encourages that indigenous peoples have a meaningful role in international forums and decision-making processes related to their rights and cultures, this includes:

- (i) supporting indigenous leaderships,
- (ii) indigenous participation in international organizations;

Acknowledges the historical injustices faced by indigenous peoples;

Emphasizes on other countries and international organizations collaborating with each other to create an unified approach to protecting indigenous cultures;

Supports fair trade initiatives that respect indigenous rights and promote sustainable development;

Recommends to provide technical support and financial support to help post-colonial nations diversify their economies;

Ensures that post-colonial nations have fair access to global markets by reducing trade barriers and supporting trade practices;

Encourages to partner with post-colonial nations to develop critical infrastructure;

Supports for sustainable agricultural practices by providing funding and expertise for programs that promote food security and environmental conservation;

Promotes the transfer of technology and knowledge to post-colonial nations which enables these countries to develop their own industries and innovate in economic-related sectors;

Recommends to invest in programs that empower local entrepreneurs and small business in post-colonial nations;

Encourages financial independence by supporting the development of local financial institutions and systems;

Highlights to enhance environmental sustainability by collaborating on initiatives that promote environmental sustainability and resilience to climate change;

Supports regional cooperation among post-colonial nations to create stronger economic blocs and reduce dependency on former colonial powers;

Suggests to develop inclusive educational policies by collaborating with governments and educational institutions that integrate indigenous knowledge and languages into national education systems;

Encourages to fund and assist in development of curricula that incorporate indigenous knowledge systems and local languages;

Promotes multilingual education programs that allow students to learn in both their indigenous languages and the dominant language(s) of their country;

Empowers to provide training, resources, and support for indigenous educators to lead the integration of their knowledge and culture into curricula;

Encourages international partners among indigenous communities, educational institutions, and governments to share knowledge and strategies for integrating indigenous knowledge and languages into education;

Advocates for funding indigenous-led schools, educational programs, and institutions that prioritize indigenous knowledge and languages;

Recommends platforms such as the United Nations to raise awareness about the importance of indigenous knowledge and languages in education;

Supports the development of digital tools and platforms to preserve and teach indigenous languages;

Advocates for funding mechanisms that specifically support the inclusion of indigenous knowledge and languages in education;

Supports initiatives that creates job opportunities and improve working conditions in developing countries;

Suggests to partner with developing countries to enhance their higher education and research institutions;

Emphasizes the engagement of diaspora communities of developing countries by creating programs that encourage them to invest in and contribute to their home countries;

Further invites collaborating with developing countries to improve working conditions, provide competitive salaries, and offer incentives such as housing, healthcare, and professional development opportunities;

Enhances by providing opportunities for continuous professional development and career advancement within developing countries;

Encourages regional collaboration among developing countries to create a larger, more dynamic labor market;

Supports to develop programs that encourage skilled professionals who have emigrated to return to their home countries;

Promotes ethical recruitment practices that discourage the exploitation of skilled professionals from developing countries;

Encourages the integration of culturally responsive teaching practices that respect and incorporate students' cultural backgrounds;

Encourages to work with educational institutions and local communities to develop curricula that are relevant to diverse cultural contexts;

Highlights on investing in the development and expansion of digital infrastructure in underserved and remote areas;

Emphasizes on the importance of educational technologies that are inclusive and adaptable to various cultural contexts;

Suggests providing training programs and resources to enhance digital literacy and technical skills among students, teachers, and communities;

Ensures that educational resources, including digital content and technology, are distributed equitably across different regions and communities;

Supports programs that involve communities and parents in the educational process, ensuring that cultural values and perspectives are integrated into education;

Suggests implementing mechanisms to regularly monitor and evaluate the impact of education reforms on cultural diversity and access to digital resources;

Recommends to establish truth and reconciliation commissions to acknowledge and document the historical injustices and abuses committed during the colonial period;

Encourages education systems to include accurate and comprehensive accounts of colonial history and its impacts;

Suggests to implement trauma-informed practices in schools, healthcare, and social services to address the psychological effects of intergenerational trauma;

Affirms action and equity programs in education, employment, and government institutions to address systemic inequalities;

Supports initiatives aimed at revitalizing and preserving the cultural practices, languages, and traditions of communities impacted by colonialism;

Empowers affected communities to lead their own development initiatives;

Promotes anti-racism education and training programs to dismantle the prejudices and systemic racism rooted in colonial legacies;

Advocates for legal and policy reforms that address the systemic inequalities created by colonial legacies;

Suggests to establish mechanisms to monitor progress and hold governments and institutions accountable for addressing colonial legacies;

Encouraging manufacturing high value goods for exporting and importing less valued goods;

ANNEXURE I

Indigenous People Bomboclat

Article 1

Definition

The 'International Agency' shall refer to 'Indigenous People Bomboclat',

The term 'UNESCO' will refer to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization,

'Documents' will refer to information about Indigenous languages, and cultures which can be used as a guide in school, students will refer to these documents to learn more about their local roots,

'Indigenous cultures and rights' will refer to all possible attributes, historical, economical, educational as well as the socio-cultural of indigenous people;

Article 2

Objective

The primary objective of this international agency would be to gather information about indigenous cultures, rights and languages, and in turn providing this to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, to help increase the knowledge of indigenous peoples and how these

documents can be used in schools to teach about indigenous cultures, rights and languages;

Article 3

Functioning

The international agency will be composed of selectively appointed Indigenous Journalists and government officials, out of which at least half the members will be Indigenous either by nationality or ethnicity,

The international agency will establish a data collection to gather information from other sources, such as testimonies and statements of Indigenous peoples, local authorities, etc,

The international agency will prepare a yearly document on the culture, languages, and rights of Indigenous peoples on the condition of Article 3 Sub Clause 4,

The drafted document will be sent to the UNESCO for review and approval,

Upon approval, the international agency will publish the document in accordance with the guidelines set by the UNESCO,

If the UNESCO suspects possible misinformation, and wishes that the international agency should look into the matter once more, they may pass a resolution by a simple majority to this effect;

Article 4

Mandates and Powers

- 1 The international agency will operate in accordance with the constitutional framework and regulations of the UNESCO Constitution,
- 2 For the purpose of document preparation , the international agency will have the mandate to access relevant information sources like government agencies, and indigenous institutions;

Article 5

Financial Composition

1. The budget of the international agency will be allocated by the UNESCO,
- 2 This budget will cover all expenses like personnel, operation costs, data collection, document preparation and publication,
- 3 The budget may be proposed by the members of the International Agency to UNESCO.

